

Phylogenetic Relationship of Kuau Raja (*Argusianus argus*) with mating behavior based on Cytochrome Genes b

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Kuau raja (*Argusianus argus*) is the mascot of West Sumatra Province which is a protected animal in Indonesia. The study of Kuau Raja is very interesting, especially since this bird has a unique characteristic. Until now the data and biological information about this king kuau is still very limited. Studies on these birds mostly focus on the ecology and behavior of these birds, for genetic studies there are still very few studies. The unique mating ring behavior of birds is very interesting to study if it is associated with phylogenetic studies. Is the behavior of the kuau raja one of the characters that distinguishes it from other taxa? And also from this behavior we can analyze the kinship relationship of the kuau raja with other species that are still in the same genus as the *Argusianus argus grayi* bird which is a bird found in Malaysia (Borneo). The phylogenetic analysis of the kuau raja as well as the study of its behavior has been previously reported, but there has been no link between the study of the kinship of the kuau bird with the mating behavior patterns of each of these species. This information will later be used as new information to compare the mating ring behavior pattern of the kuau raja bird with other species in the phylogenetic tree. The data from this can be scientific data on biodiversity and can be used as information to formulate the right strategy for the conservation of kuau raja in West Sumatra.

Both male and female kuau kings are generally active in the morning. In male Kuau activities in the mating ring consist of individual and pair activities. Individual activities include *clearing, walking, vigilance, feeding, grooming, resting, and calling*, as well as pair activities just *dancing*. While the activities of the female kuau raja consist of *resting, walking, and grooming* (Rafi *et al.*, 2022). The activity that is often carried out by the male kuau is *clearing* which aims to clean the mating ring from litter and tree branches that fall on the forest floor (Winarni, 2002). The unique pattern of behavior that can be observed from the male kuau is that during the mating season it will perform several patterns of behavior to attract female kuau. (Riani, 2011) revealed that male kuau rajas need to clean their bodies and oil their fur to keep it looking beautiful by grooming, because the cleanliness and beauty of the male's fur is an indicator of success in dancing to attract the attention of females. Rafi *et al.*, (2022) Apart from that, a unique behavior pattern, namely *calling* is an activity that is rarely observed, which is a form of male communication as a sign of territory and calls to other individuals, both male and female. The activity that is rarely carried out by male kuau rajas is *dancing* (del Hoyo *et al.*, 1994). *Dancing* begins when the male kuau raja walks closer to the female, then develops and vibrates his wing feathers in front of the female (Riani, 2011).

The results of phylogenetic analysis using *cyt b* which place the kuau raja into the peafowl (peacock) group are still in doubt. Norsyamimi *et al.*, (2020) who used the kuau raja as a comparison species in analyzing the phylogenetic relationship of *Rheinardia ocellata* (argus jambul) reported that the kuau raja is closely related to *R. ocellata* with a genetic distance of 5.7%. Phylogenetic studies that are generally used, namely the *cytochrome b gene (cyt b)*

are used to determine the taxonomic relationship of the species you want to see the kinship relationship with (Roesma *et al.*, 2019).gene sequence *cyt b* obtained will provide new information for the kuau raja in West Sumatra and to determine the genetic differences between the kuau raja species in West Sumatra and the kuau raja species in Borneo.

The relationship between *Argusianus argus* in West Sumatra and other *Argusianus argus* is monophyletic. Based on the sequence divergence value using the *cyt b* it was found that the subspecies of *A. argus grayi* in Malaysia (Borneo) and *A. argus argus* in Sumatra are different species (Cyntia, 2022). Using an ethological study we compared the mating behavior of the Sumatran kuau raja species with that of Borneo. In Borneo kuau to attract female birds , the male releases his wings in a lateral view and passes over the female bird . then flips over to the female, facing low and extending upwards until the tip touches the large funnel. The top of the wing rather than the bottom is visible to the hen and she can see the beautiful pattern of rows of ocelli. The tail is gone (Billie, 1979). Meanwhile, the kuau raja bird in Sumatra, the male bird will show off his wing feathers to form a fan (Holmes 1990). In the breeding season, the male bird shows off his wing and tail feathers in front of the female bird. Its wing feathers are opened in a fan shape, showing "hundreds of eyes" in front of its mate. Kuau raja is a polygynous animal (one male, many females). His habit is to make nests on the ground (Rudiansyah and Radhi, 2019).

The uniqueness of each species can be seen in their mating behavior, but in general, the two types of mating dance consist of 3 stages, namely the male bird sweeping the tail to the ground so that the twigs and pebbles collect to the female, then the male stands erect and erect tail feathers after which it bends regularly in front of the female (Smythies, 1960). Differences in behavior are caused by internal and external factors (Winarno and Harianto, 2013). Internal factors that influence animal behavior include genetics, morphology, psychology and physiology. While external factors include the influence of the environment around the animal or the animal's habitat (climate, predators, feed, water, space for movement, and social) (Rudiansyah and Radhi, 2019).

The phylogenetic study shows that the kuau raja has a monophyletic relationship with other types of *Argusianus argus* and by using an ethological study we compare the Sumatran kuau raja with that of the borneo have different mating behavior from that of Sumatra.. This supports the data that from the analysis of the *cyt b* gene the two types are different species. This is probably due to reproductive isolation due to the absence of gene flow, a form of allopatric speciation. So it can be concluded that *A. argus grayi* in Malaysia (Borneo) and *A. argus argus* have their own uniqueness in their mating behavior, as shown by the way the behavior of male animals attracts the attention of female animals. Information from the sexual behavior of the kuau raja provides an explanation of its reproductive biology status which is very important for the implementation of ex situ conservation activities.

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